

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component

PLCG2 Bioinformatics

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Introduction

As the bioinformatic core of TREAT-AD target prioritization, we have performed a series of analyses on drug target PLCG2 (Phospholipase C Gamma 2). These analyses include both data driven hypothesis generation using genome-wide transcriptomic and epigenomic data as well as targeted study on PLCG2 based on pathway analysis and differential expression analysis. The hypothesis generation process is also an interactive process with input from other cores in the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center based on various selection criteria which will be discussed in the later sections of this report. In addition, there are additional target candidates going through similar selection processes.

Frequent gene co-expression network mining identified microglia specific gene modules in AD

Gene co-expression network analysis is a powerful bioinformatics tool used to identify a set of genes that are involved in common biological processes, regulatory networks, and cell-specific expression. Given the large amount of publicly available gene expression datasets for AD, an important question is: are there any genes that show strong co-expression relationships in AD and human brains? By identifying genes that are co-expressed in AD, we can identify potential AD specific processes and cell types. To ensure the robustness of the analysis, we have established a mature pipeline and co-expression network mining algorithm for identifying frequently co-expressed gene modules using multiple datasets [1-3]. We have previously mined

frequently co-expressed gene modules for AD using 3-5 datasets [4, 5] and identified multiple co-expressed gene modules in AD. Here, we further expanded the frequent network mining using eight large datasets as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 | AD and normal brain transcriptomic datasets.

Dataset	AD samples	Normal samples	Brain region
GSE5281	87	74	Middle Temporal Gyrus (MTG), Posterior Cingulate Cortex (PCC), Entorhinal Cortex (EC), Hippocampus (HC), Superior Frontal Cortex (SFG), Primary Visual Cortex (VCX)
GSE48350	80	173	Entorhinal Cortex (EC), Post-central Gyrus (PCG2), Superior Frontal Gyrus (SFG), Hippocampus (HC)
GSE33000	310	157	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex(DLPFC)
GSE44772	387	129	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DLPFC), Visual Cortex (VC)
ROSMAP	224	201	Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC)
MSBB	409	273	Frontal pole (BM10), Superior temporal gyrus (BM22), Parahippocampal gyrus (BM36), Inferior frontal gyrus (BM44)
Mayo	82	78	Temporal cortex (TC)
ABA	30	56	Hippocampus(HC), Temporal Cortex (TCx), Parietal Cortex(PC), Forebrain White Matter(FWM)

By applying the algorithm and process developed in Johnson, T.S., et al [4], we identified multiple frequently co-expressed gene modules. Table 2 shows two gene modules most significantly enriched in microglia related biological processes.

Table 2. Gene modules that are strongly enriched with microglia genes. Red genes are potential candidate genes proposed by the center. The left module is identified using AD brain samples and the right module is from normal brain samples.

AD3_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74	N5_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74
<p>ABI3, ARHGAP30, ARHGDIB, ARPC1B, BTK, C1QA, C1QB, C3, C3AR1, CD300A, CD74, CD86, CSF1R, CSF3R, CTSS, CYBA, CYBB, CYTL1, DOCK2, DOCK8, FCGR2A, FLI1, FPR1, GIMAP4, GIMAP6, GIMAP8, GPSM3, HAVCR2, HCK, HCLS1, HLA-DMB, HLA-DOA, HLA-DRA, IFI30, IL10RA, INPP5D, ITGAM, ITGB2, LAIR1, LCP1, LGALS9, LILRA2, LY86, MFNG, MS4A4A, MS4A6A, MS4A7, MYO1F, NCKAP1L, PIK3AP1, PLCG2, PLEK, PTPN6, PTPRC, RHBDF2, RNASE6, SERPINA1, SIPA1, SLA, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, SLC7A7, SLC02B1, STK10, SYK, TAL1, TBXAS1, TLR2, TLR7, TMEM119, TREM2, TYROBP, VAV1, VSIG4, WAS, WDFY4</p>	<p>PLEK, LAT2, BTK, ITGB2, STEAP3, LCP1, CD86, PTPRC, PYGL, HLA-DMB, HCLS1, CD14, LY86, C3, CYBA, TYROBP, PIK3AP1, HLA-DRA, AIF1, BLNK, SYK, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, CYBB, NCKAP1L, DOCK8, HCK, TREM2, C1QA, SLA, ITGAM, FCGR2A, SCIN, WDFY4, IFI30, SERPINA1, MS4A6A, STAB1, FCGR1A, PARP9, LAIR1, DOCK2, CD300A, C1QB, FPR1, ALPK1, CASP1, CCR1, TBXAS1</p>

While both gene modules are enriched in microglia functions, the AD module is much larger with important genes such as INPP5D and PLCG2. The AD3 module also contains 18 nominated AD target genes from the Agora Wall of Target (highlighted red in the table). Pathway analysis using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) also confirmed the AD gene module is highly enriched in immune function genes, with PLCG2 as a hub gene interacting with PTPN6, CSF1R, LDL and more, as shown in the figure on the left.

PLCG2 is primarily expressed in oligodendrocyte precursor cells, but the expression is very low in other major types of brain cells.

An ideal target will be genes with low expression levels in normal brain tissues while high in AD brains. We first checked the gene expression levels for a selected group of genes of interest. As shown in the table below. PLCG2 has very low expression levels in normal brain tissues, and the single cell RNA-seq confirms that PLCG2 is only specifically expressed in the oligodendrocyte precursor cells in the normal brain tissue (see figure below, the Y-axis is the normalized counts).

Genes	Brain Expression in general (FPKM)	Highest Expression in Brain	High Expression in Tissues
INPP5D	Low (5-20)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra, hypothalamus	EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood, small intestine
PLCG2	Extremely low (2-4)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra, basal ganglia	EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood, small intestine
CSF1R	Medium (<50)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra	spleen
STAT3	Medium (<50)	Spinal cord, cerebellar hemisphere	All other tissues except brain
ABCA7	Medium (<50)	Cerebellar hemisphere, cerebellum	Whole blood, pituitary, spleen
PTK2B	High (>100)	Cerebellar hemisphere, cerebellum	Brain, EBV-transformed lymphocytes, whole blood

Due to the generally low expression level of PLCG2 in the brain tissue, there is no significant differential expression levels of PLCG2 between bulk brain tissues of AD and normal in five datasets. However, from the single nuclear RNA-seq analysis, PLCG2 is over expressed in excitatory and inhibitory neurons in various AD stages as compared to the normal brain. The results are summarized in Table 3. Using ROSMAP data on 24 AD brain samples (from early and late-stage AD patients) vs. 24 normal brain samples, PLCG2 is marginally significantly overexpressed in AD brain samples with a fold-change around 1.165 [6].

Table 3. Differential gene expression of PLCG2 in single nuclear RNA-seq for ROSMAP sub-cohort

Condition	log2 FC	Avg Expression level (Group 1)	Avg Expression level (Group 2)	Adj.P.Val
Excitatory Neuron Late AD vs. Normal	0.2137	0.0607482	0.052384201	8.60E-12
Excitatory Neuron Early AD vs. Normal	0.2172	0.060644025	0.052167998	7.04E-16
Inhibitory Neuron Late AD vs. Early AD	0.22	0.02396039	0.020571275	1.23E-03

PLCG2 functions as one of the hub gene interacting with INPP5D in immune response networks

We searched IPA for potential regulation, interactions and pathway intersections between PLCG2 and the rest of the Year1 target candidates including INPP5D (see figure below). IPA analysis identified that PLCG2 directly interacts with Year1 target INPP5D/SHIP1 and links to other AD target genes TYROBP, IL10 and several other immune response genes/proteins.

For the IPA canonical pathways involving INPP5D and PLCG2 by IPA, analysis showed the two are involved in multiple immune response pathways and phagosome formation. The x-axis of the figure is in the $-\log_{10}$ scale and thus the larger the number, the smaller the p-value for the enrichment analysis.

Canonical Pathways from IPA

Using the ToppGene tool, we also identified key pathways in which the selected genes are highly enriched, as shown below, which include interleukin signaling pathway, cytokine signaling pathway and functions in the adaptive immune system.

Targets involved pathways

Pathway	Source	No. Mol.	Total	Involved targets
IL-10 Anti-inflammatory Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	4	17	IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Interleukin signaling pathway	PantherDB	5	92	SPI1,IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
IL22 Soluble Receptor Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	3	16	IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Signaling by Interleukins	BioSystems: REACTOME	7	531	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3
Epstein-Barr virus infection	BioSystems: KEGG	5	203	SPI1,IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,PLCG2
PDGF signaling pathway	PantherDB	4	127	PDGFA,STAT3,STAT4,PLCG2
Cytokine Signaling in Immune system	BioSystems: REACTOME	7	763	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3
Osteoclast differentiation	BioSystems: KEGG	4	130	SPI1,TREM2,TYROBP,PLCG2
Bioactive Peptide Induced Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	3	43	PTK2B,STAT3,STAT4
Jak-STAT signaling pathway	BioSystems: KEGG	4	156	IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Signal regulatory protein (SIRP) family interactions	BioSystems: REACTOME	2	13	PTK2B,TYROBP
EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor resistance	BioSystems: KEGG	3	79	PDGFA,STAT3,PLCG2
JAK/STAT signaling pathway	PantherDB	2	16	STAT3,STAT4
Other semaphorin interactions	BioSystems: REACTOME	2	19	TREM2,TYROBP
Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	BioSystems: KEGG	4	270	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP
Adaptive Immune System	BioSystems: REACTOME	6	826	TREM2,PDGFA,TYROBP,CD33,INPP5D,PLCG2

PLCG2 interacts with key lymphocyte receptors and kinases

The gene ontology enrichment analysis tool, ToppGene, also revealed multiple interactions with pathways of JAK1, CSF1R, SYK, PTPN11, PIK3R1.

Interaction	No. Mol.	Total Mol.	Involved targets
JAK1 interactions	5	129	IL10RA,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
CSF1R interactions	4	47	SPI1,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
SYK interactions	5	141	PTK2B,TYROBP,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
TYROBP interactions	3	19	TREM2,TYROBP,INPP5D
PTPN11 interactions	5	253	PTK2B,CD33,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
PIK3R1 interactions	5	319	IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
IL10RA interactions	2	5	IL10,IL10RA

PLCG2 functional paralog PLCG participates in the network interaction with the inflammasome (Pycard, NALP1, caspase-1, caspase-5)

IPA analysis revealed PLCG (shown as PLC gamma in the figure below) is indirectly linked to inflammasome members through multiple types of Ig proteins.

IPA network showing possible interactions between inflammasome with our drug targets

No clear evidence of epigenetic changes for PLCG2 in AD brain tissues

We examined the histone modification H3K9Ac levels on PLCG2 promoter region in ROSMAP AD ChIP-seq data. No differential peaks associated with PLCG2 promoter region. The figure below shows genes with significantly differential acetylation.

H3K9ac Signals for significantly differential peaks

Between AD and NCI, there are H3K9ac significant signal increase in the promoters of **AIF1, ARPC1B, AXL, C1QA, HSP90AA1, MIF, SPP1, TGFB1** and significant signal decrease (FDR<0.05) in the promoters of **ANO6, HSP90AA1, LYN**. Genes with bold text are differential expression genes.

Summary of upstream and downstream interacting genes for PLCG2

Based on the IPA analysis, we Identified the immediate upstream and downstream interacting genes/proteins of PLC/PLCG/INPP5D in the canonical pathway and summarized in the figure below.

Immediate up/downstream interacting molecules from canonical pathways in IPA

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